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**THE EFFECT OF NITROGEN FERTILIZERS ON THE
TRANSPIRATION RATE OF COTTON PLANTS
GROWN IN MEDIUM AND STRONG SALINITY
IRRIGATED MEADOW ALLUVIAL SOILS**

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Abstract. This article presents information on the effect of nitrogen fertilizers on the rate of transpiration in the tillering phase of the cotton plant grown in the irrigated meadow alluvial soils of the massif of Uzbekistan, Jondor district, Bukhara region, grown on moderately and strongly saline soils.

Keywords. Moderately saline, highly saline, irrigated grassland alluvial soils, nitrogen fertilizer, transpiration rate, tillering phase.

Introduction. Transpiration is the evaporation of water by the plant body. These processes in plants are among the most important physiological processes. The transpiration rate is the amount of water that can be dispersed over one square meter of surface in one hour. These indicators are related to changes in air temperature. In the same experiment, the specific rate of transpiration in different phases of the human body is averaged at different times of the day and depends on the level of salinity and the rate of nitrogen absorption [1,2].

Material and method. The field experiment was carried out in the Jondor district of the Bukhara region, the soil was moderately and highly saline and irrigated. Among the main fertilizers used in field experiments are ammonium nitrate (NH_4NO_3 - 34.6% N), widely used as a nitrogen fertilizer, simple superphosphate with 18% P_2O_5 as a phosphate fertilizer, and potassium chloride (KCl - 60% K_2O). from potash fertilizers, obtained from local raw materials.

The transpiration rate of cotton plants grown in the experimental field was determined by weighing on a torsion balance [3].

Results and their analysis. As salinity levels increased, cotton growth was negatively affected, which ultimately affected leaf surface area and transpiration rates. For example, experiments carried out on cotton crops in medium salinity soils show that the amount of water evaporated during one hour at 8⁰⁰ in the control option without fertilizer application is 115.4 g/m², in the P₁₇₅ K₁₂₅ background option, it is 145.6 g/m² and the rate of nitrogen fertilizers together with the background. Examining the norms from 100 kg to 350 kg, we can see that the transpiration rate increased from 175.2 g/m² to 231.5 g/m² during 1 hour. When determined at 12⁰⁰ hours, the transpiration rate in the control option was 239.0 g/m², and in the background option with the specified standards of phosphorus and potassium, it was 260.9 g/m². The transpiration rate was found to be from 275.4 g/m² to 323.9 g/m² according to the nitrogen fertilizer standards mentioned above. At 16⁰⁰ hours of detection, the amount of water evaporated in the non-fertilized control was 213.4 g/m². P₁₇₅ increased to 236.9 g/m² in the K₁₂₅ -background option, and these indicators increased again when nitrogen fertilizers were applied, and the transpiration rate was 256.4 g/m² when background+N₁₀₀ kg was applied. 271.9 g/m² in the case of background+N₁₅₀, background+N₂₀₀; background+N₂₅₀; background+N₃₀₀; background+N₃₅₀ kg of transpiration rate in the used options, the amount of water evaporated in the sequence of options for one hour is 281.2; 300.9; 305.6; It was 297.7 g/m². The transpiration rate was lowest at 20⁰⁰ among the four times studied. In 20⁰⁰, we found that the transpiration rate was 63.5 g/m² for one hour in the control version of the cotton plant grown in moderately saline soils, while in the background version it was 79.0 g/m², nitrogen fertilizer rates were applied

3,4,5,6,7 In 8-variants, the rate of transpiration is 86.4 in the sequence of variants; 96.1; 102.3; 109.9; 120.4; It was 128.7 g/m².

In this salinity type, the average amount of water evaporated increased from 157.8 g/m² to 245.4 g/m² in the sequence of all options (Table 1).

Table 1

**Fast transpiration of cotton, g/m² hour
(phase buttonization)**

№	Options	Fixed hours				Average
		8 ⁰⁰	12 ⁰⁰	16 ⁰⁰	20 ⁰⁰	
Moderately saline						
1	Control	115,4	239,0	213,4	63,5	157,8
2	P ₁₇₅ K ₁₂₅	145,6	260,9	236,9	79,0	180,6
3	N ₁₀₀ P ₁₇₅ K ₁₂₅	175,2	275,4	256,4	86,4	198,3
4	N ₁₅₀ P ₁₇₅ K ₁₂₅	180,9	289,6	271,9	96,1	209,6
5	N ₂₀₀ P ₁₇₅ K ₁₂₅	195,7	297,9	281,2	102,3	219,2
6	N ₂₅₀ P ₁₇₅ K ₁₂₅	209,7	310,7	300,9	109,9	232,8
7	N ₃₀₀ P ₁₇₅ K ₁₂₅	224,8	325,0	305,6	120,4	243,9
8	N ₃₅₀ P ₁₇₅ K ₁₂₅	231,5	323,9	297,7	128,7	245,4
Highly salted						
1	Control	114,0	234,0	213,6	64,7	156,5
2	P ₁₇₅ K ₁₂₅	140,7	264,0	225,1	80,4	177,5
3	N ₁₀₀ P ₁₇₅ K ₁₂₅	169,9	272,7	245,6	86,5	193,6
4	N ₁₅₀ P ₁₇₅ K ₁₂₅	182,1	284,2	260,2	98,3	206,2
5	N ₂₀₀ P ₁₇₅ K ₁₂₅	185,2	292,6	234,7	95,6	202,0
6	N ₂₅₀ P ₁₇₅ K ₁₂₅	195,3	301,5	270,1	102,1	217,2
7	N ₃₀₀ P ₁₇₅ K ₁₂₅	220,7	312,0	280,4	105,9	229,7
8	N ₃₅₀ P ₁₇₅ K ₁₂₅	234,1	316,8	293,1	112,0	239,0

Of the salinity levels studied, the highest salinity is strongly saline soils. The results of the experiment carried out in this type of salinity show that the rate of transpiration for one hour in the control option is 8⁰⁰; 12⁰⁰; 16⁰⁰; 114.0 over 20⁰⁰ times; 234.0; 213.6; It was 64.7 g/m². In the background option, where phosphorus and potassium were applied, the amount of evaporated water during the time series studied by these indicators was 140.7; 264.0; 225.1; It was 80.4 g/m². The average

transpiration rate in the two options studied was 156.5 and 177.5 g/m² of water evaporated per hour. The transpiration rate in the studied variants with six different rates of nitrogen fertilizers was 169.9 g/m² to 234.1 g/m² at 8⁰⁰ a.m., 272.7 g/m² to 316.8 g/m² at 12⁰⁰ a.m., 245 at 16⁰⁰ a.m. 6 g/m² to 293.1 g/m². As the study continued, the rate of transpiration determined at 20⁰⁰ hours increased from 86.5 g/m² to 112.0 g/m². In highly saline soils, the rate of transpiration increased from 156.5 to 239.0 in g/m² per hour in all options.

Conclusion. The rate of transpiration is determined by the amount of water evaporated on the leaf surface. This is influenced by salinity levels and nitrogen fertilizer rates, i.e., cotton grown in non-saline soils has more leaf area than in saline soils.

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